

Quantum Mechanics and Orthonormal Basis Functions

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For quantum bound states, classical style probabilities $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ and $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ [where $W(x)=$ the wavefunction = Sum over p $a(p) \exp(ipx)$] exist. These are real and normalized to one, but unusually, they separate p and x completely. For example, $P(p)$ is the probability to find a momentum p anywhere in the system - no information about x is known. This seems to suggest that the $P(p/x)$ is not defined in a classical sense. (Similar arguments hold for $P(x)$.)

We have argued in a previous note (1), that due to a lack of time reversal balance, there is no clear classical notion of $P(p/x)$ in quantum mechanics while in classical statistical mechanics, there is a time reversal balance of two-body collisions and so $P(p/x)$ is well-defined. In particular, a momentum p collides with a p_j to form another momentum p_k . There is ambiguity if p is changing, but if at the same time a p_k is changing (colliding) back into a p at x , then the ambiguity is removed. In quantum mechanics, the ambiguity is not removed at x , but one may discern one p state from another throughout the entire x space. This suggests orthonormal probabilities e.g. say $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$. These $\exp(ip x)$ probabilities comprise the wavefunction which is linked to $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, but although Sum over p $P(p/x)=1$, $P(p/x)$ is complex with the real and complex portions taking on positive and negative values. Nevertheless, it is $W(x)$ which is the solution of the Schrodinger (and other) equations.

It is known that solutions $W_n(x)$ of the Schrodinger equation have discrete E_n (energy) values. It is possible to have $[H, \text{Operator}]=0$ and possibly to have H written in terms of this operator. In such a case, $W_n(x)$ might be both an eigenfunction of H and the Operator. Alternatively, a linear combination of Operator eigenfunctions may be used. If E_n is discrete, one may expect the operator eigenfunctions to also be discrete, leading to quantization of the Operator eigenvalues. In some cases, one may have two operators which commute with H , e.g. L_x and L_z (related to angular momentum). L_z eigenfunctions might not be linked to H so one might ask why L_z should be quantized. Another H , however, may distinguish between L_z eigenfunctions and so they also have discrete eigenvalues.

In this note, we try to consider why one should have orthonormal eigenfunctions of these commuting operators which make up the wavefunction and try to interpret their physical meaning.

Indeterminate $P(p/x)$

A characteristic of both classical mechanics and classical statistical mechanics is that one may define p at x . In classical mechanics, a particle accelerates and so its $v(x)$ continually changes, but one insists that $v(x)$ is known at x . In a classical Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, two-body elastic collisions $e_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ with $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ determine equilibrium. A particle with e_1 (hence p_1) may be interacting, forming e_3 (p_3), which leads to ambiguity in the notion of $f(e_3)$. At the same time, $f(e_3)$, however, is changing into p_1 , removing this ambiguity at a point x .

In quantum mechanics, an $\exp(ipx)$ is formed from all other $\exp(ip_j x)$ values combining with a potential and $\exp(ipx)$ has the same form for all x values. (For example, take the time-independent Schrodinger equation and write $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as Fourier series and then collect terms in $\exp(ipx)$.) There is no time reversal balance which is similar to wave interference. A wave (mechanical or probabilistic) is determined over all space and so the idea of orthonormal probability arises in order to distinguish between p values [i.e. $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ are orthonormal]. One distinguishes $P(p)$ with no x information i.e. $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In quantum mechanics, one usually speaks of eigenstates of an operator e.g. $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenstate of the momentum operator, but these eigenstates are used to construct $W(x)$ which is part of $P(p/x)$, so they seem to be orthonormal pieces of conditional probability. If p is ambiguous at x , it seems that other operators such as L_L (angular momentum) or L_z (in 3 space) should also be ambiguous for the same reason. As a result, their eigenfunctions should also be orthonormal and should interfere when forming a wavefunction, as they do.

Operators and H

In the above sections, we spoke of $\exp(ipx)$, the eigenstate of the momentum operator, but this operator often does not commute with the Hamiltonian H . It is stated in quantum mechanics that if $[H, \text{Operator}] = 0$, one may have an eigenstate $|E_n, O_n\rangle$ where O_n is an eigenvalue of the operator. The eigenstates of a Hermitian operator are orthonormal and the eigenvalues are discrete and real, just as in the case of H . (If the Operator is Hermitian, then this follows as a math property, but we ask whether there is a physical reason? H has discrete E_n values because $W(x)$ must fit certain boundary conditions (i.e. drop off near classical turning points) at the same time that $W(x)$ is made of wavelike probabilities $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to discrete E_n . In a number of cases H contains terms with the Operator present e.g. L_L . If the eigenvalues of the operator were continuous, and there is a joint eigenfunction, the eigenfunction of H would no longer be discrete. What if H commutes with an operator which is not linked to energy, e.g. L_z ? We argue that one may imagine a different Hamiltonian H_1 which does distinguish energies of different L_z values (similar to the case of spin in a magnetic field). Thus, L_z should be quantized as well.

A question arises: How does one interpret eigenfunctions of an operator in a physical way? Eigenfunctions arise in linear algebra, but what is their physical connection to a quantum problem? First, we argue that they enter in the wavefunction $W(x)$ (and from there may appear in $P(x)$, $P(p)$). Next, we note that momentum p is not well-defined at a point x in a quantum situation and the same situation seems to follow for these operators. In the case that the operator is directly linked to p , like L_L and L_z , this follows immediately. In such a case, the operator's different eigenfunctions seem to be part of $P(\text{Operator value}/x)$ and should be orthonormal exactly like $\exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, these eigenfunctions "interfere" just as $\exp(ipx)$.

Interpretation

In the above section, we argued that $W(x)$ may be written in terms of orthonormal eigenfunctions of an operator which commutes with H . The eigenvalues of the operator are not well defined at x because one value may be changing into another, hence the eigenfunctions interfere. Throughout the entire region of space, however, one may distinguish between different eigenvalues i.e. the inner product of two different eigenfunctions of the same operator is zero.

It seems that if one only uses an eigenfunction taken directly from linear algebra, then one automatically gives it a classical interpretation. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of p where p is well-defined at all points x in classical physics. Momentum is, however, not well-defined at x in a quantum scenario, leading to $\exp(ipx)$. An eigenfunction of L represents angular momentum which is well defined classically, but it is not well-defined quantum mechanically at x , otherwise one would not have different L eigenfunctions interfering (if that is the case). If one takes a single L eigenvalue, then it may be the eigenfunctions of L_z which interfere.

This seems to be linked to the Stern-Gerlach experiment. A particle seems to have spin up or down if a magnetic field is in the z direction. The spin up and down are due to quantization of projections of spin which is mathematically like angular momentum. Immediately, the classical picture of a well defined circular current perpendicular to the z axis is employed for say a spin up electron. We argue, however, that the analogous L_z eigenfunction is not well defined at x (or at an angle) in quantum mechanics, so it does not make sense to think in terms of classical scenarios which are well-defined at each x or angle. Rather, one has orthonormal basis functions (representing part of conditional probability $P(L_z/x)$ or $P(L_z/\theta)$) which interfere because of this uncertainty. (Only over all space or all angles can one really distinguish between different L_z eigenfunctions.)

Thus, if one has a spin up electron with B_z in the z direction, if one then turns on a B_x , one should have a linear combination of spin up and spin down conditional probabilities (spinors) in the B_x direction etc. One may use rotation properties of the eigenfunctions to try to deal with such scenarios (2) e.g.

$$Y(l,m)(r_1) = \sum_{m_1} D(l,m,m_1)[\text{Rotation}] Y(l,m_1)(r) \quad ((1))$$

where r_1 is obtained by rotating r .

We argue that one does not only have linear algebra as a consideration, but that one deals with conditional probabilities of an operator (e.g. L_z) at x or θ i.e. with orthonormal conditional probability functions (i.e. eigenfunctions) and takes linear combinations because one does not have a clear case of one eigenvalue or another i.e. one eigenfunction or the other at x (θ) unlike in classical mechanics. Associating the eigenfunctions of an operator whose eigenfunctions are used to create $W_n(x)$ with a classical picture leads to issues because in the classical picture the particular eigenvalue is well defined at each x or θ .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is a statistical model which does not allow one to determine $P(p/x)$ because p is continually being knocked into other p_j states by a potential and there is no balanced time reversal process occurring at a specific x . Rather a resonance exists over all of space. Thus, one may distinguish p_1 and p_2 only over all of space suggesting orthonormal conditional probability functions e.g. $\exp(ipx)$ which also happen to be eigenfunctions of p . Because of the ambiguity of p , these orthonormal probability functions can be imaginary or have positive and negative values at particular x values. $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, which are classical-like results, hold, but $P(p)$ ignores x and $P(x)$ ignores p , unlike classical physics where p and x are defined at each x point.

In quantum mechanics, one may have Hermitian operators which commute with H . In such a case, one may have orthonormal eigenfunctions $|E_n, \text{Operator eigenvalue}\rangle$. The operator eigenvalues are quantized like E_n because H may sometimes be written in terms of the operator or a new H might be. In such a case, discrete E_n requires discrete eigenvalues of the operator. We argue that the eigenfunctions of these operators are not clearly defined at x (or theta points). This follows directly if the operator is linked to p , such as L_L or L_z . In such a case, $W(x)$ is made of interfering sums of these eigenfunctions which are orthonormal only throughout all of space. One should not think of an eigenfunction of an operator, say L_z , in a classical manner because one uses a linear combination of L_z eigenfunctions due to the ambiguity at each x (theta) point. We argue that this is directly linked to the Stern-Gerlach experiment.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Wavefunction and the Identity of a Momentum State in a Quantum Bound State (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Spherical_harmonics